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Atmospheric pressure influence on the charge collection efficiency of air-vented ionization chambers in ultra-high dose per pulse electron beams for FLASH radiotherapy

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Abstract

Objective. This work studies the dependency of the charge collection efficiency (CCE) on the atmospheric pressure of commercial ionization chambers (ICs) using an ultra-high dose-per-pulse (DPP) electron beam and proves a theoretical model of this phenomenon. **Approach.** A custom-made PMMA water phantom, water- and pressure-tight sealed, was connected to a vacuum/pressure pump to vary its inside pressure from 900 hPa to 1100 hPa. ICs were placed at different depths in water and irradiated with ultra-high DPP electron beams (20 MeV, 1.2 μ s and 2.0 μ s pulse duration). Chamber signals were air-density- and polarity-corrected as a function of DPP (0.1 Gy–6.5 Gy) at different pressures. The actual DPP was determined and monitored using a calibrated PTW flashDiamond and a current transformer, respectively. Experimental CCEs were compared with numerical calculations, describing the charge transport inside ICs, including free electrons and electric field distortion. **Main results.** The CCE decreased with increasing pressure (−6%/100 hPa and −8%/100 hPa for the Advanced Markus, and Roos IC, respectively) and followed ‘logistic functions’ with DPP. The CCE₀ at a given pressure P_0 can be obtained from a CCE₁ at different pressure P_1 (scaling rule) as: $CCE_0(P_0, DPP) = CCE_1(P_1, DPP * (P_0/P_1)^2)$. Our theoretical model predicted the relative variation of the CCE with pressure, with residuals <3%. The effect can be corrected using the scaling rule even at small changes in pressure (~35 hPa), which can cause a 2% deviation on the CCE, without adding significant CCE uncertainty (~0.1%) for a DPP up to 6.5 Gy per pulse. **Significance.** This work proposes a scaling rule to correct for recombination losses dependent on atmospheric pressure in ultra-high DPP electron beams. The proposed scaling rule provides a simple, low-uncertainty correction that can be applied to empirically predetermined CCE functions, improving the accuracy of commercial IC-based dosimetry in ultra-high DPP electron beams.

1. Introduction

The charge collection efficiency (CCE), the inverse of the saturation correction factor k_s , in ionization chambers (ICs), is a fundamental parameter in determining the absorbed dose. In conventional radiotherapy, the dose per pulse (DPP) delivered is on the order of mGy (Ashraf *et al* 2020, Schüller *et al* 2020), and the charge losses due to ion recombination in up-to-date commercially available ICs

are typically between 0.1%–2%. The resulting deviations are generally compensated through the two-voltage method presented by Boag *et al* (1987), Roos and Derikum (2000), Bruggmoser *et al* (2007). From this method, it is possible to determine k_s , as reported by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) TRS-398 Code of Practice and the American Association of Physicists in Medicine Task Group 51 (Almond *et al* 1999, International Atomic Energy Agency 2024). However, this standard approach is only accurate for DPP up to 10 mGy, as shown experimentally by Petersson *et al* (2017), and later replicated computationally by Gotz *et al* (2017).

For ultra-high DPP beams, the recombination losses are considerably larger (CCE < 90% (Bourgouin *et al* 2023b)) than those observed with low DPP beams (Petersson *et al* 2017, Liu *et al* 2023a, Bourgouin *et al* 2023b), and the standard two-voltage method should not be used (Kranzer *et al* 2021), leading to new approaches to describe and correct for the ion recombination in ICs (Kranzer *et al* 2021, 2022, Gómez *et al* 2022, Paz-Martín *et al* 2022, Bancheri and Seuntjens 2024). In general, the ion recombination losses can be classified into three categories: initial recombination losses due to the electron recombination following the initial ionization event, diffusion losses due to charges collected in the opposite electrode, and volumetric recombination due to the overlapping of opposite charge carriers densities while drifting in the chamber volume (Loeb 1939, Boag 1987, Roos and Derikum 2000, Bruggmoser *et al* 2007). The latter is dependent on the ion concentration and thus on the DPP, the electrical field strength and the distance between the electrodes.

CCE in parallel plate IC exposed to pulse beams can be determined, as Fenwick and Kumar modeled (Fenwick and Kumar 2023):

$$\text{CCE} = k_s^{-1} = \frac{1}{\hat{\mu}} \cdot \ln \left(1 + \frac{\hat{\mu}}{ad} \exp \left(\frac{\hat{\mu}}{ad} \right) \left[E_1 \left(\frac{\hat{\mu}}{ad} \exp(-ad) \right) - E_1 \left(\frac{\hat{\mu}}{ad} \right) \right] \right), \quad (1)$$

where E_1 is the exponential integral function (Gradshteyn and Ryzhik 2007), a is the drift coefficient for free electrons equal to the inverse of the product of electron drift speed v_e and free electron lifetime τ , $\hat{\mu}$ is a non-dimensional parameter that characterizes the chamber through the electrode separation distance d , the applied bias U , the volume recombination coefficient α , the density number of charge carriers n_0 liberated by the radiation pulse (under reference conditions), and positive and negative ion mobilities $\mu_{0\pm}$, in the gas filling the chamber. $\hat{\mu}$ is described mathematically as:

$$\hat{\mu} = \frac{n_0 \alpha d^2}{(\mu_{0+} + \mu_{0-}) U}. \quad (2)$$

In this description, $\mu_{0\pm}$, for a reference pressure and temperature P_0 and T_0 conditions that differ from P and T , can be expressed as (Sauli 2023):

$$\mu_{0\pm}(P_0, T_0) \propto \frac{P_0}{P} \cdot \frac{T}{T_0} \cdot \mu_{\pm}(P, T). \quad (3)$$

In this sense, the ion mobility decreases, and the density of charge carriers ($n_0 \propto D_p \cdot P_0$) increases with increasing pressure, and DPP D_p . Moreover, charge losses can be expressed from Boag standard formula (Boag 1950), as

$$\text{CCE} = \frac{1}{\hat{\mu}} \log(1 + \hat{\mu}), \quad (4)$$

which can be expressed in a power series form as:

$$\text{CCE} = k_s^{-1} = 1 - \left[C_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_n \left(\frac{\rho D_p \alpha d^2}{w_{\text{air}} (\mu_{0+} + \mu_{0-}) U} \right)^n \right], \quad (5)$$

where ρ is the air mass density and w_{air} is the average energy per electron-ion pair. The first term C_0 represents the loss of charge due to initial recombination and electron/ion diffusion. The additional power series expansion coefficients are obtained from volumetric recombination being, in the standard Boag model for parallel plate chambers, $C_1 = \frac{1}{2}$, $C_2 = -\frac{1}{3}$, $C_3 = \frac{1}{4}$, etc. In the ultra-high DPP case, the volumetric recombination becomes even more significant as the DPP increases. In addition, given the presence of the high ion concentration between the electrodes, the space charge effect is more predominant in distorting the electric field inside of the ion chamber (Mie 1904, Ferreira *et al* 1975, Kranzer *et al* 2021, 2022). Therefore, the electric field strength is greater near the negative electrode and lower in the rest of the IC. As a consequence, the drift velocity of the charge carriers is modified and the recombination probability is usually enhanced, reducing the signal from the IC (Palestini *et al* 1999).

To overcome this issue, Kranzer *et al* (2021), (2022) showed that the electrode separation and the electric field strength can be adjusted to reduce the ion recombination in the charge collection process. Novel IC prototypes with reduced electrode separation have been developed (Gómez *et al* 2022, Kranzer *et al* 2022, Liu *et al* 2023a) following these initial efforts, and the results were encouraging. Gomez *et al* (2022) showed that the experimental CCE can be greater than the 99% (Gómez *et al* 2022) for DPP as large as 12 Gy, when the appropriate electrode gap and bias were selected. Petersson *et al* (2017) proposed an empirical method to calibrate three Advanced Markus chambers (PTW, Freiburg, Germany) against Gafchromic™ EBT3 film (Ashland Inc., Bridgewater, NJ) to determine the CCE for DPP up to 10 Gy in an effort to use commercial ICs in ultra-high DPP beams. This method is based on a fit of a logistic function to the measured CCE as function of the DPP D_p at the used operational bias voltage of the chamber U , mathematically described as:

$$\text{CCE} = k_s^{-1} = \frac{1}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{U}{D_p}\right)^{-\alpha}\right)^\beta}, \quad (6)$$

where α , β are free fitting parameters. The method allowed the determination of the absorbed dose to water with a reduced uncertainty (2.8%–4.0%, $k = 1$).

However, Bourgouin *et al* (2023b) recently found an indication that the air pressure could impact the CCE in addition to the aforementioned quantities. In their experimental study, the CCE of the same Advanced Markus chamber was evaluated at PTB's Metrological Electron Accelerator Facility (MELAF) and at the Swiss Federal Institute of Metrology METAS. Since the Swiss institute is located about 500 meters higher than the PTB, the measurements were carried out at different air pressures. Results revealed that the CCEs had a difference of approximately 5% between institutions at a DPP of 0.8 Gy, which was mainly attributed to a dependence of the CCE on the air pressure that the standard air density correction factor did not compensate.

In this study, we aimed to demonstrate the dependency of the CCE on air pressure conditions for commercially available ICs using 20 MeV ultra-high DPP electron beams at PTB's MELAF. Two commercial and one prototype parallel-plate type ICs were studied in the range of 0.4 Gy to 6.5 Gy per pulse (as used in FLASH radiotherapy with electrons) at different pressure conditions in the range of 900 hPa–1100 hPa (representing extreme weather conditions or 1000 m altitude) to examine differences in the CCE. We also developed a theoretical model to describe this phenomenon and to explain our observations.

2. Methods

2.1. Initial set-up

A custom-made water phantom ($30 \times 30 \times 30 \text{ cm}^3$), enclosed on all sides by PMMA walls (8 mm), was sealed water- and pressure-tight and connected to a pressure gauge (Greisinger, GMH 3161-12) and vacuum/pressure pump (KNE, N 022 AN.18) through a regulating valve in order to be able to adjust the pressure of the air in the volume above the water level inside the tank. After closing the regulating valve and switching off the pump, the pressure in the tank was stable (<0.3% change) within the time period required for a complete series of dose measurements. A triaxial bulkhead feed-through (Pomona 5178) in the top lid enabled the connection of the IC to an external electrometer outside, while the IC connector with the end of the ventilation hose was in the air volume inside the tank. In this way, the air pressure in the sensitive volume of the vented IC was in equilibrium with the internal tank pressure. A screw-on lid (20 cm diameter) on the top lid enabled access to the inside of the tank in order to change or position the IC. An additional bulkhead feed-through made contact of the water (with pinch of NaCl) in the tank with a grounding cable in order to prevent charging effects by the electron radiation.

HOLDERS were manufactured to position the ICs in the tank in the water approximately at the reference depth (at two different positions: 35 mm or 40 mm from the inner wall of the tank) as well as approximately at the dose maximum (20 mm from the inner wall). The exact depth was measured with an inside groove caliper. The change in the bulge of the front wall of the phantom due to the change of the internal pressure (<1 mm) was measured as a function of the internal pressure and taken into account when determining the water depth of the IC. However, the effect of this correction was negligible compared to the studied effects of pressure on the CCE.

The phantom was placed in front of the beam exit of the accelerators beamline with 90 cm distance between the exit window and the surface of the phantom source-to-surface distance (SSD), as depicted

in figure 1. The ICs were irradiated with ultra-high DPP electron beams (0.4 Gy to 6.5 Gy per pulse, 20 MeV, 1.2 μs and 2.0 μs pulse duration).

The thickness of the PMMA wall of the water tank, z_{pl} , was measured to be 8 mm, and for the determination of the depth in water of the chamber, its water equivalence was determined to be $z_{\text{w}} = 9$ mm using the expression (International Atomic Energy Agency 2024):

$$z_{\text{w}} = z_{\text{pl}} \cdot \rho_{\text{pl}} \cdot c_{\text{pl}}, \quad (7)$$

where ρ_{pl} , and c_{pl} are the PMMA density (1.19 g cm⁻³), and a scaling factor with a value of 0.947 for PMMA, respectively, as reported by IAEA's TRS-398 (International Atomic Energy Agency 2024). The temperature of the water was monitored using a PT100 thermometer in contact with the water inside the tank.

2.2. ICs

Three parallel-plate ICs were used to determine the CCE: a PTW Advanced Markus Chamber (TN34045, SN 002700), a PTW Roos® Chamber (TN34001, SN 003700), and a prototype IC (TN34093, SN 231495) made and provided by PTW. The latter is an ultra-thin IC (UTIC) recently designed to reduce the ion recombination in ultra-high DPP beams (Kranzer *et al* 2022).

The ICs were connected to a Keithley 616 electrometer operated in current mode. The analog output of the electrometer was recorded by means of a 16-bit analog to digital converter and from the time resolved recorded current the collected charge per beam pulse was determined. A 33 nF capacitor was connected in parallel to the input connection to keep the voltage at the input low enough even with high charge pulses from the IC during ultra-high DPP irradiation so that a linear response is ensured (Bourgouin *et al* 2023b). Charge was collected using a 400 V operating voltage with both polarities. Final charge readings were corrected for air density following the equation outlined in IAEA's code of practice TRS-398 (International Atomic Energy Agency 2024):

$$k_{\text{T,P}} = \frac{273.2 + T}{273.2 + T_0} \cdot \frac{P_0}{P}. \quad (8)$$

The reference conditions were considered to be $T_0 = 20$ °C and $P_0 = 101.32$ kPa. Similarly, readings were corrected for polarity as:

$$k_{\text{pol}} = \frac{|M^+ - M^-|}{2 \cdot M^+}, \quad (9)$$

where M^+ and M^- are the collected charges at positive and negative chamber voltage, respectively.

2.3. Radiation beam

As a proof of concept, an Elekta linear accelerator was used to irradiate the ICs in the custom-made pressure-tight water tank at conventional DPP. At conventional beams, the correction factor for air density, shown in equation (8), should correct the response of the IC for the pressure conditions ± 100 hPa

different from the reference conditions. A 20 MeV conventional electron beam was used to irradiate the ICs with a 10 cm × 10 cm field size and a beam pulse repetition frequency of 200 Hz. A horizontal beam direction was used, same as to the subsequent irradiation at ultra-high DPP. A SSD of 100 cm to the external PMMA wall (beam entrance) was used.

For the ultra-high DPP beams, experiments were carried out at PTB's research electron accelerator. A 20 MeV ultra-high DPP electron beam with a pulse duration of 2.0 μ s, and a beam pulse repetition frequency of 5 Hz was used. Here the SSD, defined as distance of the external wall of the PMMA water tank to the beam exit window of the beam line, was 90 cm or 70 cm. By optionally adding an aluminum scattering disc of 1 mm or 2 mm thickness to the 100 μ m copper exit window, and by the variation of the charge of beam pulse via current amplitude or pulse duration, the DPP at the position of the IC was varied from 0.1 Gy to 6.5 Gy per pulse. The electron beam profile at the point of measurement was Gaussian shaped (full width at half maximum of 9 cm at SSD 90 cm without scattering disc or 18 cm with 2 mm Al).

The ultra-high DPP electron beams with and without the 2 mm aluminum disc were denoted as SSD90-2-Depth and SSD90-0-Depth, respectively, for the 90 cm SSD and where Depth represents a placeholder for the position of the IC (20 mm, 35 mm, or 40 mm from the inner wall of the tank).

The pulse duration was varied from 0.5 μ s to 2.0 μ s in regular steps at fixed beam current amplitude and thus fixed instantaneous dose-rate during the pulse. The beam current amplitude was varied at fixed pulse durations (2.0 μ s, 1.2 μ s, or 1.9 μ s as well as 1.0 μ s). The pulse amplitude was varied using a metallic slit aperture with a variable slit width to intervene in the beam path. The slit width was reduced such that the pulse amplitude was reduced up to 15% of the maximum amplitude. The slit aperture is located approximately 2 m upstream from the beam exit window. A detailed description of the beamline has been provided elsewhere (Bourgouin *et al* 2022).

The sequence of measurements to determine the CCE as a function of the actual DPP was classified into three measurement courses: pulse duration variation at maximum pulse amplitude, pulse amplitude variation at maximum pulse duration (2 μ s), and pulse amplitude variation at about 60% of maximum of pulse duration (1.2 μ s).

2.4. Beam monitoring

A flashDiamond detector (T60025, PTW, Freiburg, Germany) (Marinelli *et al* 2022), calibrated in terms of absorbed dose to water by means of PTB's alanine dosimetry system in ultra-high DPP electron beams (Subiel *et al* 2024), was used to determine the DPP at the position of the IC under test. The flashDiamond detectors SN 7610 and SN 220444 used for this study has proven to respond linear ($\pm 0.5\%$) up to at least 18 Gy per pulse or 6 Gy per pulse, respectively, by comparison with alanine (Bourgouin *et al* 2022). The alanine dosimetry system has been shown to be consistent with the PTB water calorimeter primary standard also under ultra-high DPP conditions (Bourgouin *et al* 2023a). The flashDiamond detector was mounted on a motorized positioning system to determine the percentage depth dose for the ultra-high DPP beams (for each SSD with and without aluminum scattering disc). For this purpose, a phantom identical in construction to the pressure-tight one was used, but without the upper lid to have space for the motorized positioning system.

An Integrated Current Transformer (ICT) (Bergoz, Saint Genis Puilly, France) was used to measure precisely ($\pm 0.1\%$) the charge (30 nC–300 nC) of each individual beam pulse (Schüller *et al* 2017). In our setup, the ICT (in-flange version, turns ratio 50:1), is positioned in the beamline 1.3 meters upstream from the exit window. For each setup with respect to SSD, scattering disc and pulse duration, the beam pulse charge was varied and recorded as function of the simultaneously determined DPP, measured by means of the calibrated flashDiamond at the same water depths as chosen for the positioning of the IC under test. Calibration functions were then fitted to the data sets, which enabled the conversion of the measured ICT signal to the actual DPP during the charge collection measurement for the ICs with small uncertainty (1%).

Recently, current transformers have also been introduced as beam monitoring system for medical electron LINACs for FLASH radiotherapy (Oesterle *et al* 2021, Gonçalves Jorge *et al* 2022, Liu *et al* 2023b). However, some signal variations across different irradiation setups and beam parameters are reported. Pageot *et al* (2024) recently identified effects from electric fields from charge buildup in non-conductive phantoms on the nearby current transformer as reason. In our setup, the in-flange ICT is electromagnetically shielded and a ground wire in the water prevents charge buildup in the phantom.

2.5. Absorbed dose to water calculation and CCE calculations

The reading of the IC in terms of absorbed dose to water without recombination correction factor, at measurement depth z was determined as:

$$D_p^{\text{IC}} = M \cdot k_{T,P} \cdot k_{\text{pol}} \cdot k_{\text{elec}} \cdot N_{D,W,Q_0} \cdot k_{Q,Q_0}^z \cdot k_{\text{avg}} \quad (10)$$

where M is the collected charge from the IC corrected with respect to leakage current, $k_{T,P}$ is the air density correction, k_{pol} is the polarity correction, k_{elec} is the electrometer calibration factor, N_{D,W,Q_0} is the IC calibration coefficient. The beam quality correction factor k_{Q,Q_0}^z at measurement depth z is defined here as the beam quality correction factor $k_{Q,Q_0}^{z_{\text{ref}}}$ at reference depth z_{ref} , corrected by the water-to-air Spencer–Attix stopping power ratios $\frac{S_{w,\text{air}}^z}{S_{w,\text{air}}^{z_{\text{ref}}}}$, and, for the case of the beam from the research electron accelerator, by the averaging volume correction factor k_{avg} , included to correct the influence of the Gaussian shape of the beam over the response of chambers due to their geometrical differences. The beam quality correction factor can be mathematically expressed as:

$$k_{Q,Q_0}^z = k_{Q,Q_0}^{z_{\text{ref}}} \cdot \left(\frac{S_{w,\text{air}}^z}{S_{w,\text{air}}^{z_{\text{ref}}}} \right). \quad (11)$$

The product of the chamber-specific beam quality correction factor, and averaging volume correction factors $k_{Q,Q_0}^z \cdot k_{\text{avg}}$ was calculated through the EGSnrc Monte Carlo code system (Standards and ionisant, 2021) (version 4.0) using the `egs_chamber` user application (Wulff *et al* 2008) for the measurement depths. For the conventional electron beam, k_{avg} was considered to be unity.

Thus, the CCE was determined from the reading of the IC without recombination correction factor D_p^{IC} at depth z and the actual dose D_p^{ref} at the same depth, as:

$$\text{CCE} = k_s^{-1} = \frac{D_p^{\text{IC}}}{D_p^{\text{ref}}}. \quad (12)$$

2.6. Conventional beam measurement

In order to demonstrate that the air pressure in the sensitive volume of the IC in the custom-made pressure-tight water tank is the same as the pressure in the tank, the ICs under test were irradiated at three pressure conditions: 1100 hPa, 1000 hPa (room pressure), and 900 hPa using a conventional dose rate electron beam from an Elekta linear accelerator. The collected charge from the IC should increase or decrease with pressure according to the air density correction formula shown in equation (8).

2.7. Ultra-high DPP measurement

2.7.1. Calibration curves for beam monitoring

Measurements consisted of an initial calibration of the ICT against the flashDiamond detector at the same water depths as chosen for the positioning of the ICs under test for each beam setup (SSD and aluminum scatter disc) using the motorized positioning system. The actual DPP D_p^{ref} was determined with the flashDiamond while simultaneously the ICT signal was recorded. A quadratic function was fit for the actual DPP vs the ICT signal. Since the DPP is varied by the variation of the width of a slit aperture, there is a slight change in the width of the lateral shape of the radiation field and therefore, the DPP at measurement depth is not exactly proportional to the charge per beam pulse measured by the ICT. The use of a linear fit would result in a maximum deviation of 1.2%

Subsequently, the readings of the ICs under investigation were calibrated against the DPP measured by means of the ICT. The ICs were placed at the same depths as the flashDiamond, and the collected charge per beam pulse was used to determine the dose reading of the IC D_p^{IC} , as described in equation (10), as function of D_p^{ref} which was determined from the simultaneously recorded ICT signal and the respective ICT calibration function determined prior. CCE was calculated from D_p^{ref} and D_p^{IC} according to equation (12). A logistic function of the form

$$\text{CCE} = k_s^{-1} (D_p) = A_{\text{min}} + \frac{A_{\text{max}} - A_{\text{min}}}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{x_0}{D_p} \right)^h \right)^s} \quad (13)$$

was fitted to the same experimental CCE data points as function of D_p^{IC} as well as function of D_p^{ref} resulting in two functions $k_s^{-1} (D_p^{\text{IC}})$ and $k_s^{-1} (D_p^{\text{ref}})$ with different values for the free adjustable parameters

Table 1. Transport parameters used for the CCE simulations.

Transport parameter	Description
Electron velocity	Function of the electric field, simulated using Magboltz.
Electron attachment rate	Function of the electric field, simulated using Magboltz.
Ion mobilities	From Zhang <i>et al</i> (2019)
Volume recombination coefficient	$1.40 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ from Boissonnat <i>et al</i> (2016)
Electron-ion recombination coefficient	Not used.
Electron multiplication coefficient	Function of the electric field, simulated using Magboltz.
Temporal structure	Pulsed beam with a rectangular shape.
Spatial discretization	$\leq 0.5 \mu\text{m}$.
Time discretization	Adaptative.

A_{\min} , A_{\max} , x_0 , h , and s . The former is used to determine the actual DPP from the IC reading as

$$D_p^{\text{ref}}(D_p^{\text{IC}}) = k_s(D_p^{\text{IC}}) \cdot D_p^{\text{IC}}. \quad (14)$$

2.7.2. CCE experimental measurement

The irradiation measurement sequence was initially performed with the custom-made pressure-tight tank with open lid by connecting the IC directly to the electrometer. The IC was subsequently connected at closed lid (at room pressure) to the electrometer using the bulkhead feed-through. The goal of the measurements was to account for a possible impact of the unavoidable irradiation of cables and adaptors used for the bulkhead feed-through on the IC reading D_p^{IC} . Additionally, the determined D_p^{IC} was used to estimate the D_p^{ref} at the current IC position *in-situ* using the calibration curve described in the section above. The D_p^{ref} was then used to recalibrate the ICT to avoid experimental discrepancy due to possible lateral mispositioning of the IC with respect to the beam axis or beam variation from day to day.

The CCE at measurement depth was determined from the collected charge for the different pressure conditions with the actual DPP determined by means of the calibrated ICT. The aim of a second final measurement at room pressure was to account for a possible influence of moisture due to the increased humidity in the interior of the closed tank on the chamber response.

In one case the pressure was also varied from 1100 hPa to 900 hPa in regular steps at a fixed DPP. Also, in one case, the bias voltage of the Roos® chamber was varied from 100 V to 400 V to determine CCE. For each bias the pressure varied to 1100 hPa and to 900 hPa.

2.7.3. CCE theoretical model

The experimental CCE was compared to a numerical model that simulates in detail the charge transport of the charge species inside the IC. The model, described in detail by Paz Martín *et al* (2022), adequately scale the charge density released in the chamber volume and the ion, electron mobilities, and electron attachment by temperature and pressure. The transport parameters used for the simulations, described elsewhere (Paz-Martín *et al* 2025), are given in table 1.

For reference, Magboltz is a Monte-Carlo based simulation code for gaseous detectors that takes into account all the physical processes involved in the electron transport in gases. This code is able to calculate electron transport parameters such as drift velocity, attachment rate, and multiplication coefficient using tabulated electron cross sections.

3. Results

3.1. Correction factors and uncertainty

The beam quality correction factors used to determine D_p^{IC} at measurement depth for the ultra-high DPP electron beams are shown in table 2. No influence on the chamber response due to the humidity inside the water tank was observed, and no additional correction factors were needed. They were obtained with a statistical uncertainty lower than 0.2% ($k = 1$). Relative combined standard uncertainties ($k = 1$) associated with experimental CCE are shown in table 3. Experimental CCE was obtained using equations (8)–(13). The calculation of uncertainties in this work follows the description proposed by the Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology (JCGM) (JCGM 2008).

The absorbed dose to water was initially estimated using the flashDiamond detector, and the estimated relative standard uncertainty from this calibration was 0.8% ($k = 1$). Then, to determine the

Table 2. Product of chamber-specific beam quality and averaging volume correction factors $k_{Q,Q_0}^z \cdot k_{\text{avg}}$ calculated through the EGSnrc Monte Carlo for the corresponding measurement depths (20 mm, 35 mm, or 40 mm) and beam setups.

Chamber	$N_{W,D}$ [Gy nC ⁻¹]	SSD90-0-20	SSD90-0-35	SSD90-2-20	SSD90-2-35	SSD70-0-40
		$k_{Q,Q_0}^z \cdot k_{\text{avg}}$				
Advanced Markus	1.4900	0.8678	0.8909	0.8734	0.8941	—
Roos	0.0824	0.8820	0.9039	0.8754	0.8976	—
UTIC	1.3916	—	—	—	—	1.014

Table 3. Uncertainty for the experimental CCE.

Parameters	Type-A (%)	Type-B (%)	Comments
DPP (ICT)		1.0	Explained in text
$k_{T,P}$	0.18		From the standard deviation of temperature and pressure in the best and worst scenarios.
k_{pol}	0.40		From the standard deviation of charge collected
k_{elec}		0.09	Average taken from (Bourgouin <i>et al</i> 2023b).
N_{D,W,Q_0}		0.25	From calibration report
k_{Q,Q_0}^z		0.7	From Monte-Carlo calculation.
Uncertainty	0.44	1.25	
Combined Uncertainty ($k = 1$)		1.32	
Expanded combined Uncertainty ($k = 2$)		2.64	

Table 4. Relative change in the readings of the Advanced Markus with and without air density correction for 900 hPa, 1000 hPa, and 1100 hPa pressure conditions for conventional beam delivery.

Pressure (hPa)	Relative change with respect to 1000 hPa (%)			
	Advanced Markus		Roos	
	With k_{tp} correction	Without k_{tp} correction	With k_{tp} correction	Without k_{tp} correction
900	-0.1	-10.0	0.0	-10.1
1100	0.1	10.0	0.0	10.1

absorbed dose to water during the measurement course, the ICT was calibrated against the flashDiamond. The relative standard uncertainty from the ICT reading was estimated to be 0.05% ($k = 1$) for each pulse (Schüller *et al* 2017). For DPP determination, quadratic and logistic fits were used from the initial to the *in-situ* cross-calibrations for each measurement course. The relative standard uncertainty from these fits was based on the maximum deviation between the fit and the experimental values. For each detector, the uncertainty was propagated across measurements courses. Then, the uncertainty was propagated across detectors (each IC paired with the diamond) to account for both quadratic and logistic fits, and the maximum overall value (0.6%) was used as an estimator for the uncertainty of fits. Therefore, the relative combined standard uncertainty for the absorbed dose to water using the ICT monitoring system was estimated to be 1% considering the initial flashDiamond calibration.

3.2. Conventional beam delivery

The relative change of the IC signal from room pressure (1000 hPa) with and without air density correction $D_p^{\text{IC}} \cdot (k_{T,P})^{-1}$ as a function of the pressure using the conventional beam is shown in table 4. The signal without air density correction changes by 20% from low pressure to high pressure. In contrast, the percentage differences between the D_p^{IC} for the high and low pressure with respect to the 1000 hPa are less than 0.1% if the air density correction is taken into account. This result indicates that the pressure in the sensitive volume of the IC is the same as the measured pressure in the tank.

3.3. CCE for ultra-high DPP

The CCE as a function of the DPP decreases with increasing DPP in the commercial ICs traditionally used in conventional radiotherapy, as theoretically and experimentally proved in detail recently in multiple studies (Bruggmoser *et al* 2007, Petersson *et al* 2017, Kranzer *et al* 2021, 2022, Fenwick and Kumar 2023, Liu *et al* 2023a, Bourgouin *et al* 2023b, Paz-Martin *et al* 2025). The CCE for the studied chambers

Figure 2. Charge collection efficiency for the three measurement courses using the Advanced Markus (circles), Roos (squares), and UTIC (triangles) chambers with 400 V operating voltage at 1000 hPa (white), 900 hPa (red), and 1100 hPa (blue). The CCE values correspond to the measurements courses at (A) beam current amplitude variation at 1.2 μs and (B) 2.0 μs pulse duration, and (C) pulse duration variation (0.5 μs –2 μs) at maximum beam current amplitude with (SSD90-2) and without (SSD90-0) 2 mm Al scatter disc. Logistic fits (solid lines) were applied to the 1000 hPa experimental data and scaled to high and low pressure using the ratio of the pressures. The uncertainty on the CCE is 1.32% ($k = 1$), and the error bars were not plotted for clearer data visualization as they are comparable to the size of symbols.

in this work, depicted in figure 2, showed this behavior for three pressure conditions across all the measurement courses investigated.

Interestingly, the CCE curves for the 900 hPa and 1100 hPa pressure conditions did not coincide with the 1000 hPa (room pressure) at high DPP, despite the application of the air density correction factor. This result indicated that the CCE has an additional dependency on the pressure conditions of measurement that were not corrected by the air density correction factor described in TRS-398 and TG-51 protocols. For the UTIC, the CCE was measured even up to 9 Gy per pulse and it was in the entire range greater than 99% regardless of the pressure.

A logistic function, described in equation (13), was fitted to the 1000 hPa CCE experimental data (black solid curve) and then scaled to higher and lower atmospheric pressures using the pressure of the

two given experimental conditions. Under equal irradiation conditions (including pulse duration), varying only the DPP and air pressure, the CCE_0 obtained at a certain DPP D_p and pressure P_0 is estimated to be equal to the CCE_1 at a different pressure P_1 for a value of DPP that is equal to $D_p \cdot \left(\frac{P_0}{P_1}\right)^2$ as:

$$CCE_0(P_0, D_p) \approx CCE_1\left(P_1, D_p \cdot \left(\frac{P_0}{P_1}\right)^2\right). \quad (15)$$

As an example, to apply this rule correctly, at 1000 hPa the $CCE_0(D_p^{\text{ref}}) = f_0$, where f represents a logistic fit function, and CCE_0 scaled at 900 hPa is $CCE_1(D_p^{\text{ref}}) = CCE_0\left(D_p^{\text{ref}} \cdot \left(\frac{900 \text{ hPa}}{1000 \text{ hPa}}\right)^2\right) = CCE_0(D_p^{\text{ref}} \cdot 0.81)$, indicating that CCE_1 is higher than CCE_0 for the same DPP D_p^{ref} , as experimentally observed.

The dependency of the CCE on pressure for ultra-high DPP beams can be explained from the non-dimensional parameter $\hat{\mu}$ implicit dependence on pressure in equations (2) and (3). Both the electron ion mobility, and the ionization density vary with the gas mass density inside the IC linked to the pressure and temperature through the ideal gas equation. Hence, these dependencies, in combination with equation (5) makes the ion recombination depend on the product of the DPP and square of pressures as:

$$k_s^{-1} = CCE(P, D_p^{\text{ref}}) = f(D_p^{\text{ref}} \cdot P^2). \quad (16)$$

The results of the simulations also predicted a dependence of the simulated CCE values, as shown in figure 3, on the pressure conditions for the Advanced Markus and the Roos chambers for the 1.2 μs and 2.0 μs beams. The residuals between simulation and experimental data are $< 3\%$ in all cases. For the UTIC and the Roos chamber, the residuals are within $\pm 2\%$ and decrease with increasing DPP. Whereas for the Advanced Markus chamber, the residuals are within $\pm 3\%$ and the difference increase with increasing DPP.

For the Roos chamber, the simulated CCE was also investigated and compared to experimental data for different chamber voltages from 100 V to 400 V. Figure 4 shows four examples with different operation voltages than 400 V as already shown in figure 2. The residuals are within $\pm 2\%$, for all the voltages, indicating that the simulation was capable of predicting experimental CCE values for the three pressure conditions also at other chamber voltages.

For all measurements at 400 V (2.0 μs , 1.2 μs and pulse duration variation shown in figure 2) the deviations of the experimental CCE values from the fit function for the CCE at room temperature (solid black lines in figure 2) are shown in figure 5. A difference in the CCE $> 6\%$ and $> 8\%$ per 100 hPa with respect to 1000 hPa was estimated for Advanced Markus, and Roos chamber, respectively, when DPP exceed 1.5 Gy per pulse. However, significant differences ($> 2\%$) were already observed at lower DPP (0.5 Gy). These differences were even more pronounced for the Roos chamber. For the simulated CCE values, the relative difference at high and low pressure with respect to 1000 hPa showed a similar behavior as the deviation of the experimental CCE from the fit functions.

The uncertainty associated with the scaling rule, used to predict the CCE at different pressure conditions from 1000 hPa (red and blue solid lines in figures 2 and 5), was estimated through the root mean square error (RSME) for the investigated DPP range. The RSME values are included in table 5. The average (maximum) RMSE across all measurement courses was $< 2\%$ (2.9%) for the Roos IC and $< 1.2\%$ (1.7%) for the Advanced Markus IC when compared to the experimental data, as shown in figure 6. The RMSE showed a rapid increase with DPP up to 1.5 Gy and then a steadier increase higher DPP, since the CCE deviation with respect to 1000 hPa increases rapid with DPP and become steadier at DPP of about 1.5 Gy (figure 5). This trend was also observed in the scaled simulated CCE values, however, in this case the RMSE was lower than 1.6% (2.0%) for the Roos and $< 0.4\%$ (0.6%) for the Advanced Markus IC.

The average RSME for the simulated data for the Ross and Advanced Markus IC across all measurement courses was 0.8%. For the UTIC, the RMSE of simulated CCE values was $< 0.1\%$. A RMSE plot for the UTIC chamber was omitted from figure 6 as values were practically 0% for the entire DPP.

Finally, the relative change of the CCE at different pressure conditions for constant DPP of 2.5 Gy using the Advanced Markus chamber is shown in figure 7. The relative change of experimental and simulated CCE data, as a function of pressure, with respect to 1000 hPa showed good agreement within a $\pm 0.7\%$ deviation. The relative changes varied approximately 6%/100 hPa in agreement with the CCE variations presented in figure 5. However, figure 7 clearly shows that even small changes between the air pressure prevailing during the measurement for determination of a CCE or $k_s(D_p^{\text{IC}})$ function for a specific IC and the air pressure during the use of this IC can have a significant effect.

4. Discussion

The CCE showed a dependence on the pressure conditions that could not be corrected with standard air density correction factor described in literature (Bourgouin *et al* 2023b). However, this discrepancy was mitigated by using a scaling rule, whose formulation relies on the squared ratio of the pressures of two different conditions. This additional correction is negligible at conventional beam irradiation (as shown in table 4) or whenever the ion recombination effect is small as in case of the UTIC.

The results for the conventional beam showed that the air density correction was sufficient to compensate for the different collected charges due to the different amounts of ionizable air molecules in the sensitive volume of the IC at the three pressure conditions, regardless of the chamber type. Additionally, the variation on the IC signal as a function of the pressure inside the water tank demonstrated that pressure conditions could be accurately controlled and held for the duration of the measurement courses. This also applies to the measurements using the ultra-high DPP electron beam, where two opposing effects of almost equal magnitude overlap, namely the increase in the collected charge at higher pressure due to the higher amounts of ionizable air molecules versus the reduction in the collected charge due to increased ion recombination due to higher density of ions as well as decreased ion mobility.

The decrease in the CCE with increasing DPP, depicted in figures 2 and 3, was observed as expected. A difference as large as 80% in the experimental CCE values between ICs (Roos vs UTIC) at same DPP was found. This difference can be explained by the different electrode separation since a larger distance enhances the volumetric ion recombination. The Roos IC has a larger electrode distance (~ 2 mm (Bass

Figure 4. Experimental and simulated CCE data ($2.0 \mu\text{s}$ pulse duration) as a function of DPP for the Roos chamber using 100–300 V operating voltage for 900 hPa, 1000 hPa, and 1100 hPa pressure conditions. Logistic fits (solid lines) were applied to the 1000 hPa simulated data and scaled to high and low pressure using the ratio of the pressures.

et al 2009)) than the Advanced Markus IC (1 mm (Bourgouin *et al* 2023b)), and the UTIC (0.25 mm (Kranzer *et al* 2022)). As expected, the CCE increases as the distance between the electrodes is reduced. The CCE obtained using the UTIC at different pressures shows hardly any deviations from 1, the recombination losses are independent of the pressure, and pulse duration.

The level of CCE depends primarily on the DPP, but also on the pressure as hypothesized previously by Bourgouin *et al* (2023b). The decrease of the CCE with pressure for a fixed DPP is caused by two factors: a higher recombination probability due to the increased charge carrier concentration at higher air density, and a higher ion recombination probability due to the reduced mobility of positive and negative ions.

This relative change of the CCE as a function of the pressure, from 900 hPa to 1100 hPa, was adequately predicted by the simulated CCE values, as shown in figures 5 and 7, which suggests consistency between theoretical calculations and experimental observations. Figure 7 demonstrates also that even smaller air pressure changes than 100 hPa have a significant effect. The difference between a typical high-pressure weather situation and a typical low-pressure weather situation is approximately 35 hPa. This results in a CCE difference for an Advanced Markus chamber of over 2%, which, if not taken into account, is translated into a deviation of the dose reading from the actual dose. If the dosimetry laboratory (as in the case of METAS) is located 500 meters above sea level with an average air pressure that is 60 hPa lower, this results in deviations of almost 4%.

Discrepancies between simulated and experimental CCE observed across the evaluated DPP range could be due to the lack of accurate parameters available in the literature, such as ion mobilities and the ion-ion recombination constant, needed for the simulation. Different values from literature for these

Figure 5. Percentage deviation in the experimental and simulated CCE for the 1100 hPa (blue) and 900 hPa (red) pressure conditions, with respect to 1000 hPa (white) for (A) the Advanced Markus, and (B) the Roos chamber for all three cases ($2 \mu\text{s}$, $1.2 \mu\text{s}$ and pulse duration variation) shown in figure 2.

parameters can be used to reduce the differences between experimental and simulated CCE, while preserving consistency across the chambers and the bias applied. The simulations are also simplified to one dimension and additional factors in the charge collection process were not considered in the final calculation.

Additionally, the nominal parameters of the construction of the chamber, such as the electrode separation, could also deviate from the actual physical chamber, due to inherent chamber intra-model variations. For instance, for the same chamber type (intra-model variation) the CCE can vary 4% on average (at ~ 7 Gy per pulse), and as much as 20%, as reported by Bourguoin *et al* (2023b). In this context, if the electrode gap of the Advanced Markus IC is determined to be 0.95 mm instead of the nominal 1 mm, a reduction compatible with micro-CT measurements, the differences between experimental and simulated CCE values can be halved. This variation can be assumed to be within manufacturing tolerance. All these limitations could explain the differences observed between the experimental and simulated CCE values.

According to equations (3) and (5), the CCE was not only a function of the DPP, but the square of pressure (equation (16)). This simplified relationship provides a basis for the presented scaling rule. However, when the DPP increases and the electric field perturbation is no longer negligible, equation (5)

should no longer represent an adequate approximation. However, the experimental results and simulations presented in this work showed that the CCE at high and low pressure could be scaled to normal pressure, mitigating the effect of the pressure for both experimental and simulated CCE with a reduced RSME of as much as 3%, even for large DPPs.

The RSME in this analysis is the maximal deviation that can be expected in the scaled CCE from the actual CCE for a given DPP and can be considered as the accuracy of the scaling rule. The differences between the scaled CCE and the expected CCE with increasing DPP (>1.5 Gy) for the Advanced Markus and Roos chamber could be due to the exclusion of the scaling of electron transport parameters in the scaling factor proposition. However, the RMSE remained low across all measurement courses for the simulated CCE values. The difference in the RSME values between simulated and experimental CCE was likely due to the uncertainty in the acquisition of the experimental CCE.

For the UTIC case, the scaling rule was not needed, as both experimental and simulated CCE were close to 1. In the case of the Advanced Markus IC, the $>6\%/100$ hPa deviation in the simulated CCE was reduced with the scaling rule with an estimated average deviation of 0.4%. For smaller changes in pressure (~ 35 hPa) where CCE deviations can be expected to be minor ($\sim 2\%$), the scaling rule still effectively corrects the CCE. Similarly, the estimated average deviation should be reduced accordingly and to be much lower than 0.4%, approximately $\sim 0.1\%$. Overall, the scaling rule minimizes the differences in the CCE at different pressure conditions, maintaining high accuracy for three different ICs across a range of DPP.

Table 5. Maximum RMSE the scaled CCE at higher and lower pressure with respect to normal pressure, which represents the limiting cases at extreme weather conditions or 1000 m altitude.

Chamber type	Measurement course	RMSE (%)			
		1100 hPa		900 hPa	
		Experiment	Simulation	Experiment	Simulation
Advanced Markus	2 μ s	1.1	0.3	1.0	0.3
	1.2 μ s	0.7	0.4	0.8	0.6
	0.5 μ s–2 μ s	1.7	—	1.7	—
Roos	2 μ s	1.7	2.0	2.2	1.7
	1.2 μ s	1.2	1.5	1.6	1.0
	0.5 μ s–2 μ s	2.5	—	2.9	—
UTIC	2.0 μ s	—	0.03	—	0.0
	1.2 μ s	—	0.03	—	0.04

Bourgouin *et al* (2023b) hypothesized that the CCE of commercial IC at ultra-high DPP was dependent on the pressure conditions, whose contribution could not be corrected by the standard air density correction factor. In this work, we found that the CCE indeed has an additional dependency on the pressure conditions, which can influence the calculation of the recombination correction function $k_s(D_p^{IC})$ that can be determined following the method proposed by Petersson *et al* (2017). The effect was observed as a difference $>6\%/100$ hPa for the CCE curves obtained from three different pressure conditions (900 hPa, 1000 hPa, and 1100 hPa) for the advanced Markus and Roos chambers. Therefore, the pressure conditions must be specified both when determining the CCE function or $k_s(D_p^{IC})$ function for a specific IC for dosimetry at ultra-high DPP as well as when applying it. If the pressure differs significantly from reference conditions, the scaling rule should be used for correction.

The variation of the CCE with the square of pressure can be explained from the increment of charge density and the reduction of ion mobilities. This phenomenon was well summarized in the description of the non-dimensional parameter $\hat{\mu}$, as described in equations (2) and (3), which scales quadratically with the pressure. The simulations presented in this work successfully demonstrated the relative change in the CCE for the different pressure conditions tested, in accordance with the experimental observations (residuals $<3\%$). For the UTIC prototype, the recombination losses were below 1% regardless of the pressure for the entire investigated DPP range up to 9 Gy per pulse, without using additional pressure correction factors apart from air density correction equation (8).

5. Conclusions

For the Advanced Markus and Roos IC, a CCE deviation $>6\%/100$ hPa with respect to 1000 hPa was found. A simple scaling rule can be used to correct the CCE from a pressure different to a reference condition. This method is based on the ratio of the pressures of the two given measurement conditions, neglecting electric field distortions. Even small changes in pressure (~ 35 hPa) can impact the CCE ($\sim 2\%$), and the application of the scaling rule can mitigate these differences without adding a significant uncertainty (0.1%). Therefore, we recommend the use of the scaling rule to reduce the influence of the pressure on the dose measurement at ultra-high DPP with commercially available ICs using a specific $k_p(D_p^{IC})$ function. For the UTIC case, the scaling rule is not needed, as CCE is close to 1 in the studied range.

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Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary information files).

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